

On the Dynamics, Equilibria, and Economics of Gender Balance at Naturist Venues

James Junghanns

james.junghanns@gmail.com

26 February 2026 (Revision 2.7)

10.5281/zenodo.18793125

Abstract

This paper proposes a dynamical systems approach to modelling the demographic evolution of naturist venues. By quantifying gender-specific sensitivities to gender ratios, we derive an equation that governs the evolution of the system's demographic trajectory. Stability analysis reveals a fundamental asymmetry: for certain standard behavioural assumptions about the governing coefficients, the “invisible hand” does not guarantee equilibrium, but rather admits a critical “tipping point” below which the venue collapses into a male-dominated state. We further analyse the “no single male” policy as a binding mathematical constraint, using standard KKT conditions to derive the “shadow price” of female attendance and demonstrate that cross-subsidisation strategies are rational tools for both attendance- and revenue-maximisation. Finally, we apply Voronoi tessellation and percolation theory to contrast administrative constraints with intrinsic stability, demonstrating that a high-trust community configuration allows for organic growth that is inherently robust to gender-balance breaking shocks, rendering strict administrative constraints redundant in mature communities. In the conclusion, we invite the reader to reflect on whether the “no single male” policy is a necessary shield or merely a remedy for insufficient community cohesion. Methods to statistically test the model's prediction in the field are suggested and discordant observations by authorities in the field are discussed and addressed within the framework of the model.

Keywords

naturism, nudism, venues, applied mathematics, social dynamics, nonlinear dynamics, nonlinear analysis, demographics, sociology, systems of coupled differential equations.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Rachel Leigh Bugher and Tanya Jaqueline Bono for their thankless task of reading through various revisions of this text with a keen editorial eye.

My deepest thanks also goes to Professor Giovanni Mingari Scarpello for his tireless and exacting review of the logic and the mathematics present in this paper.

Last, but not least, I wish to thank naturists extraordinaire *Nick & Lins* of [9],[8] for providing their valuable feedback and the anecdotal observations made over many years of frequentation that form the core of Appendix C.

None of this would have been possible without the help provided by any of the above-mentioned and they all have my deepest gratitude.

1 Differential Model of Nativist Venue Demographics

To our knowledge, little effort has been put into quantifying or even characterising the implications and consequences of oft anecdotally discussed gender balance, or rather imbalance, observed at nativist venues. To this end, we propose a simple system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) to model the evolution of demographics at such venues based on fixed coefficients quantifying pools of potential participants' attitudes towards the ratio of genders present.

Given f females and m males, over time evolution is posited to obey

$$\begin{cases} \frac{df(t)}{dt} - \varphi_1 \cdot \frac{f(t)}{m(t)} + \varphi_2 \cdot \frac{m(t)}{f(t)} = 0 \\ \frac{dm(t)}{dt} - \mu_1 \cdot \frac{f(t)}{m(t)} + \mu_2 \cdot \frac{m(t)}{f(t)} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where φ_1 is females' preference for a higher female-to-male ratio f/m , φ_2 is females' dissatisfaction with a higher male-to-female ratio m/f , μ_1 is males' preference for a higher female-to-male ratio f/m , and μ_2 is males' dissatisfaction with a higher male-to-female ratio m/f . It is assumed, at least initially, that $\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \mu_1, \mu_2 > 0$ and that $\varphi_i, \mu_i \in \mathbb{R}^1$.

In some sense the system can be interpreted as an interplay between:

- (a) **“Comfort terms”** $f(t)/m(t)$, where a higher ratio of females to males generally increases the ‘comfort’ and perceived “social safety” for everyone attending. For females, it reduces the feeling of being stared at or being the object of unwanted attention; for males, it validates the venue as a popular, balanced social environment; and
- (b) **“Pressure terms”** $m(t)/f(t)$, where a higher ratio of males to females creates a ‘skewed’ environment. In nativist venues, a high male-to-female ratio is often perceived as ‘creepy’ or ‘unbalanced’, leading to a decrease in the growth rate of both populations (though sensitivity can vary markedly, as discussed later).

It is assumed that *a priori* no inherent gender bias in favour or against practicing nativism exists but that observed rates of participation in public venues are driven by the gender ratios themselves. We will find that females' displeasure at being in considerable minority and males' relative indifference to high proportions of their own gender can often dominate the behaviour of the system. To state the obvious, as female proportion increases, both populations experience growth (or more precisely, an influx of participants), while as male proportion increases, both populations experience decline (or efflux).

Though such a model is the bare minimum, it suffices to capture the essence of the phenomenon while remaining broadly tractable analytically and thus serving as a source of insight, rather than quantitative accuracy that would probably be better attained by other means. Nonetheless we shall find that such a simplistic model (further extended by including finite capacity) has considerable descriptive power and captures many core features observed anecdotally in the field.

In the interests of brevity and clarity the dependence of f and m on t will be henceforth dropped from discussions of (??), leading to a restatement in condensed form:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{f} = \varphi_1 \cdot \frac{f}{m} - \varphi_2 \cdot \frac{m}{f} \\ \dot{m} = \mu_1 \cdot \frac{f}{m} - \mu_2 \cdot \frac{m}{f} \end{cases} \quad \text{with } \varphi_i, \mu_i \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}. \quad (2)$$

To solve for the phase-space population trajectories, we first introduce the ratio function $r \doteq f/m > 0$ such that $f = rm$. Since the system is homogenous and of degree zero, the phase

¹These constants have units of [people · s⁻¹] = [people · becquerel] and we shall never speak of this again.

trajectories are determined by the relationship between f and m . Using the quotient rule, we can take the derivative of r :

$$\dot{r} = \frac{\dot{f}m - f\dot{m}}{m^2} = \frac{\dot{f}}{m} - \frac{f}{m} \cdot \frac{\dot{m}}{m}. \quad (3)$$

Substituting the expressions for \dot{f} and \dot{m} gives:

$$\dot{r} = \frac{1}{m} \left(\varphi_1 - \frac{\varphi_2}{r} \right) - \frac{r}{m} \left(\mu_1 r - \frac{\mu_2}{r} \right). \quad (4)$$

Factoring out $1/m$ and distributing r gives us

$$\dot{r} = \frac{1}{m} \left(-\mu_1 r^2 + \varphi_1 r + \mu_2 - \frac{\varphi_2}{r} \right). \quad (5)$$

To find trajectories in the (m, f) plane we eliminate time t by taking the ratio of the two original ODEs and then simplify by multiplying both numerator and denominator by the term f/m , and finally using $r = f/m$:

$$\frac{df}{dm} = \frac{\dot{f}}{\dot{m}} = \frac{\varphi_1 \frac{f}{m} - \varphi_2 \frac{m}{f}}{\mu_1 \frac{f}{m} - \mu_2 \frac{m}{f}} = \frac{\varphi_1 \left(\frac{f}{m}\right)^2 - \varphi_2}{\mu_1 \left(\frac{f}{m}\right)^2 - \mu_2} = \frac{\varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2}{\mu_1 r^2 - \mu_2}. \quad (6)$$

Now we isolate the variables m and r to perform integration:

$$m \frac{dr}{dm} = \frac{\varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2}{\mu_1 r^2 - \mu_2} - r = \frac{\varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2 - \mu_1 r^3 + \mu_2 r}{\mu_1 r^2 - \mu_2}. \quad (7)$$

Separating the variables gives us:

$$\frac{\mu_1 r^2 - \mu_2}{-\mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2} dr = \frac{dm}{m}. \quad (8)$$

The integral on the left depends on the roots of the cubic polynomial

$$P(r) \doteq r \cdot \left(\mu_2 + \varphi_1 r - \mu_1 r^2 - \frac{\varphi_2}{r} \right) = -\mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2; \quad (9)$$

and two cases are worth distinguishing:

- (a) **Fixed Rays** when $P(r) = 0$ has a positive real root r^* then $dm/dr = 0$ which represents a straight-line trajectory in phase-space where $f = r^* \cdot m$ that function as an attractor to which general curves tend to or away from, but cannot cross; and
- (b) **General Curves** where $\dot{r} \neq 0$ the trajectories will curve towards or away from those fixed rays, defining the non-equilibrium dynamic flow of the naturist venue's population levels.

The one-line take-away is that in this system of ODEs modelling gender balance at naturist venues equilibria are ratios of relative populations and not specific values. Curious readers can experiment with how the system responds to various combinations of parameters by using the interactive demonstration available on the *Wolfram Demonstrator* platform[5].

Global Stability and Phase Dynamics

Figure 1: Global stability and phase dynamics showing streamlines converging toward the attractor ray. The attractor in this case is depicted as having a high relative proportion of females compared to males. Isoclines are trivially computed by setting $\dot{f} = 0 \implies \sqrt{\frac{\varphi_1}{\varphi_2}} < 1$ and similarly $\dot{m} = 0 \implies \sqrt{\frac{\mu_1}{\mu_2}} > 1$.

1.1 Stability of Phase-Space Solutions

Recalling (3) we have that applying the quotient rule on $r = f/m$ gives

$$\dot{r} = \frac{\dot{f}m - \dot{m}f}{m^2} = \frac{1}{m} (\dot{f} - r\dot{m}). \tag{10}$$

Substituting the system (2) yields

$$\dot{r} = \frac{1}{m} \left[\left(\varphi_1 r - \frac{\varphi_2}{r} \right) - r \cdot \left(\mu_1 r - \frac{\mu_2}{r} \right) \right]. \tag{11}$$

Combining denominators by multiplying within the bracket by r/r gives us the equation that governs the overall evolution of the gender ratio:

$$\dot{r} = \frac{1}{mr} \cdot \left(-\mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2 \right) = \frac{1}{mr} \cdot P(r). \tag{12}$$

Since the population m and the ratio r are strictly positive quantities, the sign of the rate of change of r depends entirely on the characteristic polynomial $P(r)$ from (9). The equilibrium points of the system are the roots r^* where

$$P(r^*) = 0. \tag{13}$$

Not all equilibria are stable, however. To determine long-term fate of the venue, we analyse the stability of these roots by examining the derivative of the growth-rate \dot{r} / dr at the equilibrium point itself. Using the chain rule on (12):

$$\left. \frac{d\dot{r}}{dr} \right|_{r=r^*} = \frac{\frac{dP}{dr}}{mr^*}. \quad (14)$$

Since the prefactor $1/(mr^*)$ is always positive, the stability is determined solely by the slope of the polynomial $P(r^*)$ as it crosses the axis:

- If $P'(r^*) < 0$ this r^* is a **stable attractor** because the polynomial slopes downwards towards this root, ensuring that any deviation will be self-correcting. This represents the venue’s “social equilibrium” ratio. It is the value around which the venue’s gender balance will naturally cluster.
- If $P'(r^*) > 0$ this r^* is an **unstable repulsor** because as the polynomial slopes upwards, any deviation will be self-reinforcing. This can be thought of as representing a “critical ratio”. If the ratio falls beneath this critical value, the self-reinforcing feedback loop takes hold and accelerates until a single gender dominates (which we shall subsequently argue will likely be all-males).

In general, we have three distinct demographic behaviours:

- If $P(r) > 0$ then the proportion of females increases;
- If $P(r) = 0$ the system is in equilibrium and the relative proportions remain constant;
- If $P(r) < 0$ the proportion of males increases.

Let us investigate the extrema of $P(r)$ in order to characterise its behaviour and thus perform boundary analysis keeping $m, f > 0$ because the model is undefined on the axes.

At $P(0) = -\varphi_2$ because all other terms are factors of r . Since φ_2 (female exit rate) is positive, $P(0)$ must be negative. Demographically this implies that if the ratio is very low, the change \dot{r} in the rate r is negative, the system will be driven towards total collapse ($r = 0$) and there is no mechanism of endogenous recovery from this final population of zero.

At $r \rightarrow \infty$ (infinite females) the leading term $-\mu_1 r^3$ dominates. Since μ_1 (male influx) is positive, $P(r) \rightarrow -\infty$. The demographic interpretation is that if somehow the female population were to become overwhelmingly predominant, a correspondingly oversized male influx will inevitably bring the ratio back down. The term $-\mu_1 r^3$ also dominates when $r \rightarrow -\infty$ (infinite males), but the sign flips, presumably causing a mass exodus and bringing the population to zero.

As the curve defined by $P(r)$ begins negative at $r = 0$ and goes to negative infinity at arbitrarily large r , there are three cases, of which two scenarios are likely for a venue:

- No positive roots imply a “doomed venue” where the coefficients of $P(r)$ are such that its local maximum remains below zero, and thus \dot{r} is always negative. Demographically this entails that irrespective of how many females attend initially, the ratio will relentlessly decrease until the female population vanishes.
- Two positive roots imply a “viable venue” where the attraction parameters (φ_1, μ_2) are strong enough relative to the “exit/entry” pressures to make the cubic curve bulge upwards and cross the axis twice at roots that we shall denote r_1 and r_2 . We can characterise these roots on the basis of the gradient of $P(r)$.

- The repeated double root corner-case implies a “**dicey venue**” because $P(r) \approx -a(r - r^*)^2$ (where a is the tangent at the local maximum) and thus $P(r) \leq 0$ on both sides of r^* (strictly negative except at the root). In reality we do not expect to observe such a scenario as it is so inherently unstable as to be likely merely transient.

The lower root r_1 is a “viability threshold” where the curve makes its first crossing from negative to positive territory. Its slope is positive and this is an *unstable repulsor*, and the dynamics are as follows:

- If the system begins slightly below this root ($r < r_1$), $P(r)$ is negative and $\dot{r} < 0$ so the system will be pushed down towards zero (collapse of the female population).
- If the system begins slightly above this root ($r > r_1$), $P(r)$ is positive and $\dot{r} > 0$ so the system will be pushed upwards towards the second root. This is the “critical ratio” the venue must stay above in order to remain viable.

The upper root r_2 is a “natural equilibrium” where the curve would make a second crossing from positive territory back into negative values. The slope here is negative and it is a *stable attractor*: if the system is above this value, $\dot{r} < 0$ (the ratio increases), and if the system is below this value, $\dot{r} > 0$ (the ratio decreases). This represents the long-term destiny of the venue: as long as the ratio stays above this threshold, the demographics will naturally settle here.

Summarising the stability analysis, the general condition for a sustainable naturist venue in this model is that the polynomial $P(r)$ must have a local maximum greater than zero. We can find the local maximum by solving

$$P'(r) = -3\mu_1 r^2 + 2\varphi_1 r + \mu_2 = 0. \tag{15}$$

If the value of $P(r)$ at this maximum is positive, the venue will survive and maybe thrive. If it is negative, it is destined to fail.

Figure 2: The Geometry of Viability: Phase Dynamics and Viability Thresholds. The cubic polynomial $P(r)$ must cross the axis to create a stable equilibrium r_2 . The lower root r_1 acts as a critical threshold. Jointly they define the band within which the venue can retain a viable gender ratio.

1.2 A compact proof of stability

Because the system is homogenous of degree zero, stability of an equilibrium ray r^* is governed by the scalar

$$\eta(r_2^*) = \left. \frac{d\dot{r}}{dr} \right|_{r=r_2^*} = P'(r_2^*) < 0. \quad (16)$$

This is geometrically equivalent to requiring that the flow of the vector field across the ray is directed inwards.

When $\varphi_2 = 0$, the cubic polynomial (9) loses its constant term and can be factored as $P(r) = r \cdot (-\mu_1 r^2 + \varphi_1 r + \mu_2)$, so immediately $P(0) = 0$; furthermore when $\varphi_2 = \mu_2 = 0$, (9) can be further factored as $P(r) = r^2 \cdot (-\mu_1 r + \varphi_1)$: intuitively enough, if efflux coefficients vanish, growth dominates as without sensitivity to pressure terms, there is nothing holding participants back.

Conversely, if the trajectory slope is steeper than any ray when above it, the gap widens.

This can be fully formalised as follows: to determine if an equilibrium r^* is stable, we examine the response of the system to a small perturbation ϵ . Let $r = r^* + \epsilon$. Linearising the system around the fixed point:

$$\dot{\epsilon} \approx \epsilon \cdot \left. \frac{d\dot{r}}{dr} \right|_{r=r^*}. \quad (17)$$

From equation (12), noting that $P(r^*) = 0$, the derivative simplifies to:

$$\left. \frac{d\dot{r}}{dr} \right|_{r=r^*} = \frac{1}{mr^*} \frac{dP(r)}{dr}. \quad (18)$$

Since $m, r^* > 0$, behaviour in the neighbourhood is determined strictly by the slope of the polynomial $P(r)$ at the root.

- If $P'(r^*) < 0$, then any perturbation decays, and the equilibrium is **stable**.
- If $P'(r^*) > 0$, then any perturbation grows, and the equilibrium is **unstable**.

(Sophisticated readers will note that this is essentially an eigenvalue argument without the need to roll out the heavy artillery of vector calculus.)

1.3 The effects of male indifference to male predominance

Intuition guides us into believing that males have a relatively high tolerance for predominantly male demographics $\mu_2 \approx 0$. We can harness this intuition and make males totally indifferent by setting $\mu_2 = 0$. This represents a venue where males do not depart even if females are vastly outnumbered. This changes the dynamics significantly: without the ‘‘pressure relief valve’’ of males departing, the venue is much more prone to gender collapse should the female population diminish.

When $\mu_2 = 0$, the governing polynomial loses its linear term: $P(r) = -\mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2$. The function has a local maximum at $r_{max} = \frac{3\mu_1}{2\varphi_1}$ and in order for this venue to continue being viable, this peak must be positive ($P(r_{max}) > 0$), leading to the inequality

$$P(r_{max}) > 0 \iff \frac{4\varphi_1^3}{27\mu_1^2} - \varphi_2 > 0 \iff \varphi_1^3 > \frac{27}{4}\mu_1^2\varphi_2. \quad (19)$$

We are able to solve for the population trajectories in this scenario. From (8) we know that

$$\frac{dm}{m} = \frac{\mu_1 r^2}{-\mu_1(r - \rho_1)(r - \rho_2)(r - \rho_3)} dr. \quad (20)$$

Cancelling μ_1 and by means of partial fraction decomposition we have:

$$\frac{r^2}{(r - \rho_1)(r - \rho_2)(r - \rho_3)} = \frac{k_1}{r - \rho_1} + \frac{k_2}{r - \rho_2} + \frac{k_3}{r - \rho_3} \quad (21)$$

(where coefficients k_i are derived from the roots in the manner of $k_1 = \frac{p_1^2}{(\rho_1 - \rho_2)(\rho_1 - \rho_3)}$ & cetera). Integrating both sides gives us the exact shape of the curves in the phase portrait:

$$m(r) = C_0 \cdot |r - \rho_1|^{-k_1} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{-k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_3|^{-k_3}. \quad (22)$$

We are remarkably also in a position to calculate $t(r)$: how long it takes a venue to reach a given gender ratio (including the special case $t(0)$, the moment of collapse). We do this by substituting $m(r)$ into the male rate equation $\dot{r} = dm/dt = \mu_1 r$ to obtain:

$$t(r) = \frac{1}{\mu_1} \int_{r_0}^r \frac{1}{s \cdot m(s)} dm. \quad (23)$$

Since $dm = m \frac{\mu_1 s^2}{P(s)}$ we can rewrite this as

$$t(r) = \int_{r_0}^r \frac{m(s) \cdot s}{P(s)} ds. \quad (24)$$

For illustrative purposes, consider the following “death spiral” scenario, wherein a venue starts with an initial ratio r_0 slightly below the threshold ρ_2 . $P(r)$ will be negative, so \dot{r} will also be negative, and so the ratio begins to slide downwards. As it approaches $r = 0$, ever-smaller values of r cause the constant term $-\varphi_2$ to dominate the polynomial, and the rate of decline of \dot{r} becomes approximately proportional to $1/r$. A crash finally occurs because the integral converges to a finite value, meaning that the female population doesn’t just asymptotically fade away; it actually *hits zero in finite time*.

1.4 Regarding Closed-form Solutions in the Time Domain

We have seen that the trajectory of the population in the phase plane is determined by the integral relation between m and r :

$$\int \frac{dm}{m} = \int \frac{\mu_1 r^2 - \mu_2}{P(r)} dr. \quad (25)$$

Here $P(r) = -\mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2$ from (9) is a full cubic polynomial. In order to solve this integral analytically, we must perform a partial fractional decomposition, which in turn requires factoring the denominator into the form $-\mu_1(r - \rho_1)(r - \rho_2)(r - \rho_3)$. Though solvable in general, the symbolic expressions for these roots involve nested cube roots of complex discriminants (Cardano’s formulæ). Substituting these large symbolic expressions into the exponents of a power-law solution renders the result opaque and algebraically rather intractable. Without first quantifying the coefficients, we cannot know if the roots are real, or complex; distinct, or repeated.

This, unfortunately, is but the first and most easily dealt-with impediment. Even in fortunate or contrived circumstances where we find coefficients that yield three clean, real roots (e.g. $r \in \{1, 2, 3\}$), we are immediately met with a more formidable issue: inversion.

Let us assume, for the sake of argument, that we have found a solution $m(r)$. To find time evolution $r(t)$, we must solve the integral in (24). Solutions will invariably take the form of a sum of logarithmic and perhaps polynomial forms:

$$t(r) = A \log_e |r - \rho_1| + B \log_e |r - \rho_2| + C \log_e |r - \rho_3| + D. \quad (26)$$

To find explicit functions $f(t)$ and $m(t)$ we must invert this equation to find r as a function of t . Unfortunately an equation of the form $t = \log_e(r) + \log_e(r - k)$ is not generally expressible in elementary closed form; typically only implicit forms exist and special functions are required. The solution $r(t)$ notionally exists, but it will be a non-elementary implicit function often involving the *Lambert W* function or ‘worse’ for multiple logarithmic terms. Therefore, no general closed-form formula for $f(t)$ can be given for this model. We are forced to rely on parametric descriptions of the form $(t(r), f(r), m(r))$.

While the general case is intractable, there are specific constraints on the coefficients that simplify the algebraic treatment enough for explicit solutions to be written down.

If we assume males are indifferent about the gender ratio when entering (as discussed previously) then $\mu_1 = 0$, and thus the term $-\mu_1 r^3$ vanishes from $P(r)$ which then becomes a quadratic equation

$$P_2(r) = \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2. \quad (27)$$

Roots are then found easily via completion of the square or the quadratic formula. Integration leads to simpler inverse trigonometric or hyperbolic functions (such as \arctan and artanh) which can sometimes be inverted to find $r(t)$ explicitly.

Indeed, we can calculate that:

$$\int \frac{dm}{m} = \int \frac{-\mu_2}{\varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2} dr \quad (28)$$

leads to the solution²

$$\log_e m = K - \frac{\mu_2 \arctan\left(\frac{r\sqrt{\varphi_1}}{\sqrt{\mu_2 - \varphi_2}}\right)}{\sqrt{\varphi_2}\sqrt{\mu_2 - \varphi_2}}. \quad (29)$$

If, on the other hand, we adopt a very ‘egalitarian’ standpoint where female and male sensitivities are identical ($\varphi_1 = \mu_1$ and $\varphi_2 = \mu_2$), the numerator and denominator in the phase trajectory will often share factors, which in turn means that the ratio evolution \dot{r} might simplify to a constant or a simple power law, potentially allowing for trivial solutions such as linear growth $r(t) \propto t$. This might be plausible in certain scenarios, such as in cultures where *Freikörperkultur* (FKK) is broadly accepted and unremarkable or when females and males rigidly attend as couples. (We shall return to this in another guise in due course.)

We have already analysed the intuitively “indifferent males” ($\mu_2 = 0$) scenario, and though $P(r)$ remains a cubic, the loss of the linear term r often simplifies the root structure considerably. Hybridising the previous two simplifying cases, if females were to also become indifferent to being in stark minority ($\varphi_2 = 0$) this would further simplify root structure, but until we have a reason to presume otherwise, observation and intuition suggest that φ_2 is large and significant, probably due to unfortunately not unfounded expectations of obnoxious and even predatory male behaviour. (We shall return to this in that same altered guise mentioned above.) Solutions would be parametric as the inversion problem would still exist³.

²This has the disadvantage of not being elegant, but also has the advantage of being borderline-tractable if one is into this kind of thing. We choose to shield easily impressionable readers from the full horror that is laid bare, but those who wish to proceed down this dark path are free to undertake the voyage with our blessing of safe return.

³The interested reader is referred to Appendix A for a suitable transformation approach.

2 Forcing Viability: the “*No Single Males*” policy

We have so far discussed “free entry” models, where the influx of females and males were independent functions of the current ratio r : with natural female participation given by

$$J_f^{nat} = \varphi_1 \frac{f}{m} = \varphi_1 r, \quad (30)$$

and correspondingly natural male participation will be

$$J_m^{nat} = \mu_1 \frac{f}{m} = \mu_1 r. \quad (31)$$

To formalise the “no single males” policy sometimes enforced by certain venues, we will model the venue as an optimiser facing a binding constraint. The policy dictates that female attendance must equal or exceed male attendance $J_f \geq J_m$. In the strictest and most draconian interpretation, we force $\dot{f}_{in} = \varphi_1 r \geq \dot{m}_{in} = \mu_1 r$, thus creating a system with a binding constraint.

In this scenario of constraint dynamics, evolution of the male population is now governed by the minimum of “natural influx” and thus “policy limit”:

$$\dot{m} = \min(\mu_1 r, \varphi_1 r) - \frac{\mu_2}{r}. \quad (32)$$

Assuming the venue is popular enough that male demand is unconstrained and thus wish to enter at a higher rate than females do (i.e. $\mu_1 > \varphi_1$ which is anecdotally not unreasonable and the root cause of the instability we modelled previously), the policy constraint becomes binding.

The system of ODEs that models the system shifts to:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{f} = \varphi_1 \cdot r - \frac{\varphi_2}{r} \\ \dot{m} = \varphi_1 \cdot r - \frac{\mu_2}{r} \end{cases} \quad \text{with } \varphi_i, \mu_1, r \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}. \quad (33)$$

(Note that in the expression for \dot{m} μ_1 has been replaced by φ_1 .)

Recall from (10) that $\dot{r} = \frac{1}{m}(\dot{f} - r\dot{m})$. Substituting the constrained male rate changes yields:

$$\dot{r} = \frac{1}{m} \left[\left(\varphi_1 r - \frac{\varphi_2}{r} \right) - r \cdot \left(\varphi_1 r - \frac{\mu_2}{r} \right) \right]. \quad (34)$$

This simplifies to the modified version of (12), the equation that governs the overall gender ratio when the constraint is binding:

$$\dot{r} = \frac{1}{mr} \cdot \left(-\varphi_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2 \right). \quad (35)$$

The original destabilising cubic term $-\mu_1 r^3$ has been replaced by the ‘policy’ term $-\varphi_1 r^3$. As we generally assume $\mu_1 > \varphi_1$ (males are more eager to attend than females), replacing μ_1 with φ_1 significantly flattens the downward curve of the cubic polynomial $P_{policy}(r)$. This pushes roots towards the left, effectively lowering the critical threshold required for viability. ***Effectively, by tying male entry to female entry, policymakers artificially slow the rate of male growth to match the female ‘comfort’ growth rate and ensure the ratio is always viable by rationing male attendance.*** The venue cannot become ‘oversaturated’ with males by the process of entry, only via differential exit (which we suppose to be comparably negligible). As we have seen, μ_2 can be argued to be essentially zero, and under these circumstances φ_2 likely would not exceed it.

2.1 Shadow Costs: Unlocking the Value of Others

In the unconstrained region (where the constraint is slack and not effective) the ‘cost’ of entry is zero (or the nominal access fee). However, when the constraint binds ($\hat{m}_{in} = \hat{f}_{in}$ despite $\mu_1 > \varphi_1$), we have *excess male demand* for admission.

There is now a difference between the number of males who wish to enter and the number who are granted access:

$$\Delta J_m = (\mu_1 - \varphi_1) \cdot r. \quad (36)$$

The *shadow price* λ represents the marginal value of a female entrant, as every female who enters the venue ‘unlocks’ a corresponding slot for a male, and thus the presence of a female acquires measurable economic value equal to the profit that could be generated by that unlocked male entrant.

We have already seen that unconstrained female attendance is $J_f^{nat} = \varphi_1 \cdot r$ in (30) and that unconstrained male attendance is $J_m^{nat} = \mu_1 \cdot r$ in (31), however due to policy constraints aimed at curtailing instability actual male attendance J_m cannot exceed female attendance J_f :

$$J_m \leq J_f. \quad (37)$$

In this “excess male demand” scenario, the venue is turning away males that are willing to pay in order to be granted access, depressing its revenues.

Since J_m is capped by J_f , total attendance is determined solely by female demand J_f and can be at most $2J_f$. For every single female who chooses to enter, one further male is admitted. We can optimise this in two distinct manners.

2.2 Scenario A: Maximisation of Revenue (Z)

Consider the venue to be a commercial operator seeking to maximise total revenue Z (a proxy for profit and economic utility). The objective function is

$$Z \doteq P_f \cdot J_f + P_m \cdot J_m \quad (38)$$

where P_i represents access fees paid by each demographic to the venue.

To ensure the optimisation problem is well-posed and demographically meaningful, we must bound the domain. While our model still admits a venue having an infinite capacity, the market that it draws from does not. Therefore we model the venue’s market as a geographic Voronoi cell defined by travel-time or travel-cost distance relative to competing venues. Within this finite catchment area with finite population, there exists a maximum number of female and male guests (f_{max} and m_{max} respectively), and thus the optimisation occurs on the compact domain $[0, f_{max}] \times [0, m_{max}]$. Consequently, our objective function is continuous on a compact set, guaranteeing the existence of a global maximum by the Extreme Value Theorem[11], thereby discarding unphysical asymptotic solutions. We introduce the catchment constraints $f < f_{max}$ and $m < m_{max}$ and assign the multipliers ν_f and ν_m respectively.

Under these constraints and the binding policy, the effective constrained revenue function becomes:

$$Z_{constrained} \doteq P_f \cdot J_f + P_m \cdot J_f = (P_f + P_m) \cdot J_f. \quad (39)$$

Under this scenario, the marginal value of one additional female guest is no longer just her access fee P_f , but rather it has now become:

$$\frac{\partial Z}{\partial f_{in}} = P_f + P_m. \quad (40)$$

To rigorously ground this result, we invoke the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions ([6],[7]). Let $\lambda \geq 0$ be the Lagrange multiplier associated with the policy constraint $g(J_f, J_m) =$

$J_m - J_f \leq 0$. The Lagrangian for the venue’s maximisation problem is:

$$\mathcal{L}(J_f, J_m, \nu_f, \nu_m) \doteq P_f J_f + P_m J_m - \lambda(J_m - J_f) - \nu_f(J_f - J_f^{nat}) - \nu_m(J_m - J_m^{nat}). \quad (41)$$

The first-order stationary condition with respect to female entry (in the minimisation convention) is

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial J_f} = P_f + \lambda = 0. \quad (42)$$

or, more simply, the marginal value is increased by λ . When the constraint is binding (male demand for access is exceeding the quota), the shadow price λ exactly equals the marginal revenue of excluded males (P_m), which should be subject to a highest-bidder auction in order to preferentially satisfy those who most desire to attend. Consequentially, the effective marginal value of a female guest becomes

$$V_f = P_f + \max(P_m). \quad (43)$$

This multiplier λ represents the formal economic justification for subsidies to support female attendance such as the schemes described in [10]: the subsidy creates a positive externality every time an additional female is enticed to attend, and to maximise total surplus, it must internalise this externality by subsidising her entry up to the value λ . The male premium pays for the female subsidy to relax the binding constraint.

2.3 Scenario B: Maximisation of Attendance (W)

Contrast this with a community-run venue seeking to maximise total participation and welfare W of its attendees, approximated here by total attendance

$$W \doteq J_f + J_m. \quad (44)$$

The optimisation problem is distinct, and the binding constraint yields the result

$$W_{constrained} \doteq 2J_f. \quad (45)$$

To maximise attendance and welfare, the community venue *must also* maximise female influx J_f as each additional female *still* unlocks a corresponding male vacancy.

Thus we arrive at a powerful conclusion: under the constraints of the “no single male” policy, the incentives of revenue-maximisation and welfare-maximisation are perfectly aligned. In both scenarios, the optimal strategy is invariant: the female guest is the limiting resource, and just as her preferences φ_1, φ_2 govern her propensity to attend, her shadow price governs the potential scale of the venue’s overall attendance and acquires value as the finite resource that unlocks attendance and through that, revenue, in a context of induced scarcity. To the authors it seems more likely that since both optimisations are subject to the same bottleneck of induced scarcity, both optimisations inevitably seek to relieve the same constraint. That it results in being the constraint that can, *through additional mechanisms*, lead to revenue-maximisation is just a logical consequence: the W maximisation is inherent in the Z maximisation. To some this seems transparent; others view it as transparently conspiratorial. We will let the reader decide which camp they are in, but we invite them to withhold making a decision until venues’ finite capacity is discussed presently.

2.4 Trading Off: Marginal Rates of Substitution

Marginal Rates of Substitution (MRS) describes and quantifies the trade-off required to maintain a constant level of “social utility” (or growth stability) at a venue.

Let us define the utility of female guests for the venue U_f as equivalent to the growth rate of female attendance (a proxy for comfort/attractiveness of the venue):

$$U_f(f, m) \doteq \dot{f} = \varphi_1 \frac{f}{m} - \varphi_2 \frac{m}{f}. \quad (46)$$

The MRS is thus the answer to the question: “if we add one male (increasing discomfort), how many females must we add to keep the overall comfort level unchanged?” The slope of the iso-comfort curve $dU_f = 0$ is given by:

$$\frac{\partial U_f}{\partial f} + \frac{\partial U_f}{\partial m} = 0. \quad (47)$$

Taking the partial derivatives results in:

$$\frac{\partial U_f}{\partial f} = \frac{\varphi_1}{m} + \frac{\varphi_2 m}{f^2}, \quad \frac{\partial U_f}{\partial m} = \frac{\varphi_1 f}{m^2} - \frac{\varphi_2}{f}. \quad (48)$$

Solving for the gradient df / dm we find:

$$MRS_{f,m} = -\frac{df}{dm} = \frac{-\left(-\frac{\varphi_1 f}{m^2} - \frac{\varphi_2}{f}\right)}{\frac{\varphi_1}{m} + \frac{\varphi_2 m}{f^2}}. \quad (49)$$

Multiplying both numerator and denominator by m gives:

$$MRS_{f,m} = \frac{\varphi_1 r + \varphi_2 / r}{\varphi_1 + \varphi_2 / r^2} = r \cdot \left(\frac{\varphi_1 r^2 + \varphi_2}{\varphi_1 r^2 + \varphi_2} \right) = r \quad (50)$$

and thus,

$$MRS_{f,m} = \frac{f}{m}. \quad (51)$$

This should come as a surprise to nobody. In demographic terms, this means that in order to maintain the exact same level of comfort, the substitution rate is simply the current ratio. This both confirms and follows from iso-clines (lines of constant growth) being rays from the origin. To keep the comfort constant, the venue must expand population linearly along the ray.

3 Full House: Finite Carrying Capacity

So far, our model has assumed unconstrained supply at infinite-capacity venues. However, as every physical venue⁴ has a hard finite total carrying capacity T (determined, amongst other things, by locker counts, sun-beds, limited accommodation or camping pitches, pool safety limits, or fire codes). Unlike biological and demographical systems where growth slows due to resource scarcity (the dampening effect of the Verhulst logistical model[14], for example), a venue usually hits a hard constraint when whatever limiting resource is fully subscribed. Furthermore, as potential attendees are neither being born nor dying according to the abundance or scarcity of resources, but are simply turned away when T is reached, it seems preferable to implement a “turnstile model”⁵: not a damping term on the parameters, but a boundary condition on the domain. The system evolves according to its governing equations until the total population $f + m = T$. We can formalise this as a constraint on the total number of attendees:

$$f + m \leq T. \quad (52)$$

3.1 Dynamics at Capacity: the “Churn Mechanism”

Once the venue is full and the constraint

$$f + m = T \quad (53)$$

holds, dynamics switch from growth to replacement. We must also be careful to maintain the demographic balance between f and m in order to avoid a “death spiral” by ensuring demographics must settle on the stable attractor ray

$$f = r^*m. \quad (54)$$

We are going to solve for the point that satisfies both conditions simultaneously. Substituting the stable ratio constraint (54) into the capacity constraint (53) results in:

$$m + r^*m = T. \quad (55)$$

We can factor out m to obtain

$$m \cdot (1 + r^*) = T, \quad (56)$$

and solve for the male equilibrium population m^*

$$m^* = \frac{T}{1 + r^*}, \quad (57)$$

and then substitute back into (54) to find the female equilibrium:

$$f^* = \frac{Tr^*}{1 + r^*}. \quad (58)$$

This point (f^*, m^*) represents the only sustainable “full occupancy” rate scenario. If a venue reaches capacity at a different ratio, the system is in one of two conditions:

⁴With the notable exception (maybe) of nude beaches.

⁵There is an additional issue of information asymmetry that further fortifies this reasoning: naturist venues, by their very nature, tend to be private and enclosed and thus not easily viewable from outside. This entails that prospective entrants presenting themselves at the gate will be unaware of the current level of attendance or crowding inside the venue’s borders. Consequentially only gatekeepers who are aware of the venue’s internal occupancy rate are in a position to moderate attendance accordingly. This difficulty of observation does not necessarily contradict the whole premise of the model, in that globally the model works correctly even if pressure terms act internally upon having observed the conditions and comfort terms act by word of mouth or reputation. Again nude beaches might be argued to be an exception.

Equilibrium at Finite Capacity

Figure 3: When capacity is constrained by a maximum T , the system is characterised by a rapid adjustment of the gender ratio toward the attractor ray r^* . As shown by the sample trajectory from a female-heavy state, the system’s evolution is arrested at the capacity constraint, resulting in a stable equilibrium. Note that $m < m_{max}$ so $f + m \leq T$, $r > r^*$ can hold.

- If $r \leq r^*$ the venue has a female-heavy demographic. The venue is stable and saturated but admissible males cannot gain entry. If the venue differentiates price by gender and subsidises female attendance, it is leaving revenue on the table.
- If $r < r^*$ the venue has a male-heavy demographic and is in the unstable ‘repulsor’ zone. In a regime of mere replacement, the system cannot auto-correct: suppose the venue hits capacity with a male-dominated ratio $r < r^*$. Males, whom we assume have lower sensitivity to gender imbalance $\mu_2 \approx 0$ are unlikely to leave. However, females, feeling crowded out and in discomfort, will exit ($\dot{f}_{out} > 0$). These female exits create new availability for new entrants which by definition will have to be females, because at capacity any vacancy created by a female is going to be reserved for the entry of a new female guest (who must be unaccompanied, as accompaniment by a male would not only fail to restore the ratio but also exceed the constraint). However, replacing dissatisfied females with other dissatisfied females does not restore equilibrium but maintains the $r < r^*$ imbalance.

In order to avoid this, the venue must most likely run at $f + m < T$ (below capacity), sacrificing some immediate revenue in order to prevent irrecoverable female population collapse. This is plausible but also somewhat unforgiving, as the mathematics of the model apparently indicate that naturist venues are perennially teetering on the edge of collapse if a queue of willing females are not clamouring outside to replace their sistren as soon as they leave. Since successful venues

are observed and in reality seem to be broadly stable, we must seek a mechanism that makes the solutions more robust to ratio shocks.

PREPRINT

4 The Topology of Comfort

To understand why the specific constraint $r \leq 1$ is so frequently advocated, we must look beyond aggregate demographics and examine the detailed social topology of the venue. The ‘comfort’ of a female guest, and specifically her ability to remain largely indifferent to the males present ($\varphi_2 \approx 0$) is not merely a psychological trait, but an indicator of her local connectivity to other attendees and her social horizon.

We can model the venue floor as a stochastic Voronoi tessellation[15]. A “safe space” for a female guest can be tentatively defined topologically: she feels secure if she is part of a couple or if she belongs to a connected component of other female guests large enough to form a “social shield” against isolation or encirclement. This maps the problem to percolation theory.

Maintaining Sightlines

Case when $r > \frac{1}{2}$: Connected female network Case when $r < \frac{1}{2}$: Shattered female network

Figure 4: Here we conceptually see that a female-rich ratio $r \gtrsim \frac{1}{2}$ allows $p_f \gtrsim \frac{1}{2}$ and thus a robust female social graph may emerge providing “comfort in numbers”.

It is a known result[2] in stochastic geometry that the critical probability threshold \mathcal{P}_c for the emergence of a “giant component” (a connected subgraph) on a Voronoi tessellation is $\mathcal{P}_c = 1/2$. If p_f represents the probability that a random guest is female, a robust, connected female network only exists if $p_f \geq 1/2$. Expressing this in terms of our ratio $r = f/m$ we find:

$$p_f = \frac{f}{f+m} = \frac{1}{1+1/r} \iff 1 \geq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1/2}{r} \iff r \geq 1. \quad (59)$$

This result provides the physical justification for the behavioural parameters and the empirically observed success of the “no single males” policy: the assumption that females can be “at ease” and tolerant of a slight predominance of male strangers is valid as long as this giant component is somewhere in the neighbourhood of plausibility, however it may be subconsciously computed or intuited: we suggest the mechanism may be as basic as females preserving lines of sight to fellow females. Since $p_m = 1 - p_f$, the obvious conclusion is that if $p_f > p_m$, females can remain confident that males will be unable to create a “giant male component” of their own and “gang up” on them. At $r \approx 1$, $p_f \approx 1/2 \iff p_m \approx 1/2$ meaning that odds are relatively matched. Thus the constraint $r \geq 1$ preserves the topological integrity of the female social graph in conditions of uncertainty. Below this ratio ($r < 1$) the female network undergoes a

phase-transition and shatters into isolated, vulnerable, encircled clusters, likely elevating the effective φ_2 as a defensive mechanism.

4.1 When women are at ease

We have stated that it is fairly intuitive to assume that $\varphi_2 \gg 0$ because, anecdotally, females may be made uneasy by expectations of inappropriate male behaviour and therefore seek “comfort in numbers”. We have also noted that when in a couple, $\varphi_2 \approx \mu_2 \approx 0$. For economy of argument, let us now return to the free-entry model, as the effects of finite supply have largely been understood. Recall that gender ratio dynamics are governed by the cubic (9) with equilibria at (13). If we implicitly differentiate the root, we find that

$$P(r_i, \varphi_2) = 0 \iff \frac{dr_i}{d\varphi_2} = -\frac{\partial P/\partial \varphi_2}{P'(r_i)} = \frac{1}{P'(r_i)}. \quad (60)$$

This has a remarkable consequence: a rising φ_2 causes the two positive roots to move towards each-other until they coalesce into a saddle-node at the boundary case where $P(\varphi_2) = 0$. When $\varphi_2 = 0$ we have that for $P(0) = 0$ and a small $r > 0$ the following approximation holds:

$$P(r) \approx \mu_2 r + \varphi_1 r^2 > 0, \quad (61)$$

which in turn means that in these circumstances $\dot{r} > 0$ and thus *the gender ratio r is pushed upwards rather than being sucked into collapse*, and indeed the reader can verify that

$$\varphi_2 = 0 \iff P(r) = \mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r = r \cdot (-\mu_1 r^2 + \varphi_1 r + \mu_2). \quad (62)$$

Thus we have that for small $r > 0$, $P(r) \approx \mu_2 r > 0$, $\dot{r} > 0$ and this we can interpret as a welcome impediment to triggering the “death spiral” discussed previously. Mathematically this breaks homogeneity because now there is a root at $r = 0$ and the sign flips; demographically this frees the venue from the “tyranny of the origin” whereby every r^* must pass through $(0, 0)$.

This explains why we very frequently observe that small, high-trust groups (such as, for example, four or five heterosexual couples) at a venue can easily accommodate a ratio-breaking event such as the arrival of a single male or a male homosexual couple. This is fully compatible with the compact proof of stability presented earlier.

φ_2 is a coefficient associated with tolerance for being in the minority, but is likely first and foremost a measure of justified female concern with inappropriate male behaviour.

This is likely why couples exhibit $\varphi_2 \approx \mu_2 \approx 0$ behaviour: because the female in a couple feels safe from inappropriate attention. If a norm of male propriety could be strictly enforced, the system can literally “get off to a good start” where high trust and ease create an environment that is receptive to stable growth and far more robust to imbalance than we had heretofore considered⁶.

Combined, the two effects described in this section explain why amongst strangers or unaccompanied, females prefer a ratio that does not disfavour them heavily, while when assembled in a group they can form a stable comfort network or at the very least have constant lines of sight amongst each other, while in an environment of trust, the system loses that characteristic sensitivity we had identified previously as being overly conservative to the point of exaggeration.

⁶This is not to be confused with the “dicey venue” third case described earlier, and is in many ways its opposite.

Figure 5: By breaking the homogeneity assumption ($\varphi_2 \approx 0$), the attractor ray is no longer constrained to intersect the origin. The resulting phase flow exhibits robust attraction even in the absence of perfect gender balance.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a dynamical systems approach to modelling the demographics of naturist venues. By quantifying gender-specific preferences for, and sensitivities to, population ratios, we derived an equation that governs evolution of the venue’s social balance and subsequent modifications thereto.

Our analysis yields three principal theoretical conclusions:

1. **Inherent Instability:** The proverbial “invisible hand” does not guarantee a balanced gender ratio and to some extent can punch a venue in the groin. We identified the existence of a critical unstable root below which the venue enters a “death spiral” of male-dominated stagnation. This indicates that in conditions of rigid preferences, passive management is insufficient because a venue cannot organically “grow its way out” of a bad initial ratio if our intuitions about typical coefficients are correct ($\varphi_2 \gg 0, \mu_2 \approx 0$).
2. **Shadow Price of Balance:** By modelling the “no single males” policy as a binding constraint, we derived KKT conditions for the system. We demonstrated that under this constraint, the shadow price of a female entrant includes the opportunity cost of the male entrants she enables. This provides a rigorous economic justification for cross-subsidisation (e.g. “ladies free” pricing), showing that revenue maximisation (Z) and community participation (W) effectively converge on the same strategy: prioritising female attendance and participation.
3. **The Determinism of Capacity:** We showed that when a venue reached its physical carrying capacity T , the final equilibrium (f^*, m^*) is strictly determined by the intersection of the stable gender ratio and the carrying capacity border.

This model suggests that a naturist venue is not merely a static facility but a complex social reactor that is sensitive and either needs to be managed or incorporate some self-regulating mechanism. It suggests that care must be exercised when priming the naturist venue with its first participants, and that seeding the initial population with couples and/or a selection of females who are largely indifferent to being outnumbered by males ($\varphi_2 \approx 0$) can go a long way towards avoiding the scenarios of gender collapse when imbalance sets in beneath the critical ratio r^* that would ordinarily trigger the “death spiral” process. What appears to the authors more likely than active management is that venues derive from high-trust communities that are relatively insensitive to at least small shocks to the gender ratio and that grow serenely until male misbehaviour actually becomes a tangible issue.

5.1 On the “No Single Male” policy: motivation and consequences

Some remarks about the “no single male” policy are in order, as it is notoriously contentious. Given the model and the assumptions about the coefficients that govern it, it is shown to be an effective policy to prevent collapse of the female population from which there is no endogenous return. Whether a venue chooses to adopt it or not is largely down to their values and whether the preferences of their prospective female guests make the prospect of female attendee collapse a realistic scenario that warrants guarding against. As noted above, priming the venue with couples is one such mechanism; alternatively even a small “hard-core” kernel of female participants unconcerned by males significantly outnumbering them can provide the bedrock that in turn could allow slightly more sensitive females to participate⁷. While the mathematical model emphasises the primacy of female preferences and behaviours, it is likely that male behaviour and attitudes are a determining factor in how at ease females feel at

⁷Modelling this is beyond the scope of the present paper as modelling φ_2 to be a function of r is a significant complication worthy of future study.

venues and therefore how inclined they are to stay as opposed to depart when gender ratios are unbalanced in their disfavour.

The “no single male” policy is not a fundamental requirement for comfort: it is an engineering control that compensates for insufficient trust and weak norm enforcement. In high-trust settings, females’ discomfort parameter effectively vanishes as does that of their male counterparts, and the venue can tolerate male-skewed ratios provided females are not locally isolated or encircled. In low-trust settings, the same local-connectivity condition is more fragile, so the policy appears necessary because it preserves the “giant female component” (social shielding) by restricting male access and in turn preventing the formation of a “giant male component” that may induce unease.

We have also proven that when surrounded by a close-knit community they trust, females can accommodate growth that disfavours them provided it does not become overwhelming. This is presumably the process by which long-standing naturist communities took root: by beginning with trust and being extended with mutual respect.

5.2 Stepping back

In closing, the authors would like to make a final remark: if the reader is uncomfortable with the rational economic consequences that derive from the “no single male” policy as described in this paper, *in primis* the emergence of a rational incentive to promote and incentivise female attendance through asymmetric pricing that makes participating females themselves “objects of pursuit”, then the reader cannot consistently advocate in favour of that policy.

Though never explicit, “no single males” introduces a form of rationing and artificial scarcity which objectifies female participants by giving their presence economic value: stability is introduced but at the great social cost of making females a precious finite resource. This should cause us to pause and reflect. Perhaps the way forward is to adopt norms of male behaviour that place female participants at ease and enforce them strictly. Making females’ participation a commodity to be bought (even at an invisible shadow price) is not in the interests of the broader naturist community to whom such a consequence should be antithetical to the point of rejecting the premise, as we advocate.

Appendix A: Closed-Form Solutions to Transformed Systems

A.1 A Temporal desingularisation and a general time-domain solution by quadratures

We can make inroads into the time-domain analysis by separating the *geometry* of the ratio dynamics from the *clock* that converts the ratio evolution into physical time. Let our $r(t) \doteq f(t)/m(t)$ exist in $U = (0, \infty)^2$.

A.2 A Sundman time-change removes the prefactor in \dot{r}

From the quotient rule one obtains

$$\dot{r}(t) = \frac{1}{m(t)r(t)} P(r(t)), \quad P(r) \doteq -\mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2. \quad (63)$$

The denominator $m(t)r(t) = f(t)$ is purely a *time-scaling* factor. Introduce a new time parameter τ (dual time) by the Sundman transformation[13]

$$\frac{d\tau}{dt} = \frac{1}{m(t)r(t)} = \frac{1}{f(t)} \iff \frac{dt}{d\tau} = f(\tau). \quad (64)$$

Then by the chain rule,

$$\frac{dr}{d\tau} = \frac{dr}{dt} \cdot \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \left(\frac{1}{mr} P(r) \right) \cdot (mr) = P(r). \quad (65)$$

Hence the ratio dynamics are a one-dimensional *polynomial flow* in dual time.

A.3 General solution structure (no factorisation required)

Equation (65) is separable, so $r(\tau)$ is determined implicitly by

$$\tau - \tau_0 = \int_{r_0}^{r(\tau)} \frac{du}{P(u)}, \quad r_0 = \frac{f_0}{m_0}. \quad (66)$$

Once $r(\tau)$ is known, the populations can be recovered by quadrature. Using (64),

$$\frac{dm}{d\tau} = \dot{m} \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \left(\mu_1 \frac{f}{m} - \mu_2 \frac{m}{f} \right) \cdot f = m \cdot (\mu_1 r^2 - \mu_2),$$

so

$$m(\tau) = m_0 e^{\left(\int_{\tau_0}^{\tau} (\mu_1 r(\sigma)^2 - \mu_2) d\sigma \right)}, \quad f(\tau) = r(\tau)m(\tau). \quad (67)$$

Finally, physical time is recovered from (64) by

$$t(\tau) = t_0 + \int_{\tau_0}^{\tau} f(\sigma) d\sigma = t_0 + \int_{\tau_0}^{\tau} r(\sigma)m(\sigma) d\sigma. \quad (68)$$

A.3.1 Lebesgue/measure formulation of the physical clock (optional but useful)

Define a positive set function on Borel sets $E \subseteq [\tau_0, \infty)$ by

$$\nu(E) \doteq \int_E f(\tau) d\tau. \quad (69)$$

Then (68) becomes $t(\tau) = t_0 + \nu((\tau_0, \tau])$. In particular,

$$t_\infty \doteq \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} t(\tau) < \infty \iff \int_{\tau_0}^{\infty} f(\tau) d\tau < \infty, \quad (70)$$

which provides a clean criterion for when an ‘‘infinite dual time’’ process can still terminate (or hit a boundary state) in finite physical time.

Applying it to the model

To find the exact phase-space curve for female population, we divide \dot{f} by \dot{r} to eliminate time:

$$\frac{df}{dr} = \frac{\dot{f}}{\dot{r}} = \frac{\frac{\varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2}{r}}{\frac{P(r)}{f}} = f \cdot \frac{\varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2}{r \cdot P(r)}. \quad (71)$$

Separating variables yields the defining integral of the female population:

$$\frac{df}{f} = \frac{\varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2}{r \cdot P(r)} dr. \quad (72)$$

Assuming the roots of the cubic $P(r)$ are ρ_1 , ρ_2 , and ρ_3 , partial fractions separate an exact $1/r$ term:

$$\frac{df}{f} = \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{k_1}{r - \rho_1} + \frac{k_2}{r - \rho_2} + \frac{k_3}{r - \rho_3} \right) dr, \quad (73)$$

where the terms k_n are generated as before⁸. Integrating both sides yields the female phase-space equation

$$f(r) = C_f \cdot r \cdot |r - \rho_1|^{k_1} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_3|^{k_3}. \quad (74)$$

In dual time τ , the ratio evolves simply as

$$d\tau = \frac{dr}{P(r)}. \quad (75)$$

Inverting the transformation to get real-time t , we substitute directly:

$$dt = \frac{f(r)}{P(r)} dr. \quad (76)$$

This gives the female time-domain integral:

$$t(r) = \int \frac{C_f \cdot r \cdot |r - \rho_1|^{k_1} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_3|^{k_3}}{-\mu_1 r^3 - \varphi_1 r^2 + \mu_2 r - \varphi_2} dr. \quad (77)$$

Following the same procedure it is possible to construct an analogous implicit expression for $m(r)$, finally yielding:

$$\begin{cases} f(r) = C_f \cdot r \cdot |r - \rho_1|^{-k_1} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{-k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_3|^{-k_3} \\ m(r) = C_r \cdot |r - \rho_1|^{-k_1} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{-k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_3|^{-k_3}. \end{cases} \quad (78)$$

Since r_0 is specifically defined as $r_0 = f_0/m_0$, it follows that $C_0 = C_f = C_m$.

All things said, the authors do not consider this particularly useful but have included it as an example of how such systems can be tackled.

⁸ $k_n \doteq \frac{\mu_1 \rho_n^2 - \mu_2}{3\mu_1 \rho_n^2 - 2\varphi_1 \rho_n - \mu_2}$.

Appendix B: Statistical Estimation of Parameters

Though the model is explicitly a toy for coarsely modelling phenomena, a key question for empirical verification is whether the theoretical coefficients $(\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \mu_1, \mu_2)$ can be recovered from real-world data collected in the field, and if, once estimated, they lead to observables that coincide with the results derived in this paper.

While a single observation of a venue's gender balance (observing an instantaneous r or more likely r^* because we can expect most going concerns to be in equilibrium) presents an identification problem because an infinite set of parameter combinations can yield the same root, a time-series of attendance provides sufficient variation to estimate coefficients. Recall the original model formulated in (??) and (2).

For a discrete time-series (taken at hourly or daily intervals, for example) we approximate the instantaneous rate of a gender $\dot{g}_{f \vee m}$ as the finite difference:

$$\Delta g_{t, f \vee m} \doteq g_{t+1, f \vee m} - g_{t, f \vee m}. \quad (79)$$

That can be arranged into a standard linear regression model of the form

$$Y \doteq \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 + \epsilon. \quad (80)$$

B.1 Estimating female coefficients φ_1 and φ_2

Let the dependent variable be the net change in females:

$$Y_{f,t} = f_{t+1} - f_t. \quad (81)$$

Let the independent variables be the current ratios:

$$X_{1,t} = \frac{f_t}{m_t}, \quad X_{2,t} = \frac{m_t}{f_t}. \quad (82)$$

We estimate the regression

$$Y_{f,t} = \varphi_1 X_{1,t} - \varphi_2 X_{2,t} + \epsilon, \quad (83)$$

where the regression coefficient for $X_{1,t}$ gives the estimate for φ_1 and the coefficient for $X_{2,t}$ gives the estimate for $-\varphi_2$.

B.2 Estimating male coefficients μ_1 and μ_2

Similarly, let

$$Y_{m,t} = m_{t+1} - m_t. \quad (84)$$

We estimate

$$Y_{m,t} = \mu_1 X_{1,t} - \mu_2 X_{2,t} + \epsilon. \quad (85)$$

B.3 Data Requirements

To obtain statistically significant estimates, the data must contain **variance in the ratio** r . If, on the other hand, a venue is perfectly managed and always sits at equilibrium $r^* = f^*/m^*$, the regressors X_1 and X_2 will be unchanging constants. Similarly, if observations are made in situations where there is no influx or efflux such as on a nude cruise. In these cases regression will suffer from perfect collinearity, rendering the coefficients unidentified.

Valuable data is generated when the system is out of equilibrium. An “event study” approach analysing days when the ratio is externally perturbed (e.g., a bachelor or bachelorette party arrives or departs) provides a useful exogenous shock to trace out response curves (X values) and the system's correction (Y values).

B.4 Implied Structural Tests

Once the coefficients are estimated from the data, the theoretical “Survival Inequality” (19) derived in this paper can be empirically tested. Though derived from what is explicitly a toy model amenable to analysis, it would be nonetheless interesting to ascertain to what degree this inequality qualitatively and quantitatively describes actual observations in the field.

Appendix C: Anecdotal observations from authoritative observers indicate male-to-female ratios of 60% : 40% are commonly observed at viable naturist venues

Nick & Lins who run the *Naked Wanderings*[9] and *Destination Clothes Free*[8] YouTube channels are well-known authorities in the naturist community. In private communication they indicated that they have frequently observed male-to-female ratios of 60% : 40% indicating $r \approx 2/3$.

Assuming $\mu_2 = 0$ in order to reduce the degrees of freedom of the system, we have

$$P(r) = \mu_1 r^3 - \varphi_1^2 - \varphi_2, \quad (86)$$

which in turn implies

$$P(0) = 0 \iff -\mu_1 \left(\frac{8}{27}\right) + \varphi_1 \left(\frac{4}{9}\right) - \varphi_2 = -8\mu_1 + 12\varphi_1 - 27\varphi_2 = 0. \quad (87)$$

and thus

$$\varphi_1 = \frac{2}{3}\mu_1 + \frac{9}{4}\varphi_2. \quad (88)$$

The stability condition ($P'(2/3) < 0$) implies the derivative for stability becomes stricter because the term μ_2 has been set to zero, leading to:

$$P'(r) = -3\mu_1 r^2 + 2\varphi_1 r. \quad (89)$$

$$P'\left(\frac{2}{3}\right) = -3\mu_1 \left(\frac{4}{9}\right) + 2\varphi_1 \left(\frac{2}{3}\right) < 0 \iff -\frac{4}{3}\mu_1 + \frac{4}{3}\varphi_1 < 0 \iff \varphi_1 < \mu_1. \quad (90)$$

The window of viability for the typical observed venue is thus

$$\frac{2}{3}\mu_1 < \varphi_1 < \mu_1. \quad (91)$$

We can perform the obvious algebraic manipulations to give us the maximum tolerable female efflux under these circumstances:

$$\frac{2}{3}\mu_1 + \frac{4}{9}\varphi_2 < \mu_1 \iff \frac{9}{4}\varphi_2 < \frac{1}{3}\mu_1 \iff \varphi_2 < \frac{4}{27}\mu_1 \approx 0.148\mu_1. \quad (92)$$

Appendix C.1 Phase-space solutions in terms of r for observed 3 : 2 male-to-female ratio under the $\mu_2 = 0$ assumption

Given these constraints, recalling (22) we can promptly derive the relative populations in terms of r :

$$\begin{cases} m(r) = C_0 \cdot |r - \rho_{unstable}|^{-k_1} \cdot |r - \frac{2}{3}|^{-k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_{negative}|^{-k_3} \\ f(r) = r \cdot m(r) = r \cdot C_0 \cdot |r - \rho_{unstable}|^{-k_1} \cdot |r - \frac{2}{3}|^{-k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_{negative}|^{-k_3}. \end{cases} \quad (93)$$

Because the suppressed characteristic polynomial $P(r) - \mu_1 r^3 + \varphi_1 r^2 - \varphi_2$ is governed by the roots $\{2/3, \rho_{unstable}, \rho_{negative}\}$ and are insufficiently constrained to be a single value but are rather a potential *range* of values, we can only rely on the pair-wise products:

$$\frac{2}{3}\rho_{unstable} + \frac{2}{3}\rho_{negative} + \rho_{unstable} \cdot \rho_{negative} = 0. \quad (94)$$

Rearranging gives:

$$\rho_{unstable} \cdot \rho_{negative} = -\frac{2}{3}(\rho_{unstable} + \rho_{negative}). \quad (95)$$

Now define a *strength term*

$$S \doteq \frac{\varphi_1}{\mu_1} - \frac{2}{3}, \quad (96)$$

leading to solutions

$$\rho_{unstable} = \frac{S + \sqrt{S^2 + \frac{8}{3}S}}{2}, \quad \rho_{negative} = \frac{S - \sqrt{S^2 + \frac{8}{3}S}}{2}. \quad (97)$$

Appendix C.2 What if $\mu_2 \neq 0$ after all?

Allowing $\mu_2 \neq 0$, the condition for the slope of the polynomial to be negative (and thus stable) at $r = 2/3$ becomes

$$P'\left(\frac{2}{3}\right) < 0 \iff -4\mu_1 + 4\varphi_1 + 3\mu_2 < 0. \quad (98)$$

which can be rearranged to give

$$\varphi_1 < \mu_1 - \frac{\mu_2}{2}. \quad (99)$$

Phase-space solutions are now

$$\begin{cases} m(r) = C_0 \cdot |r - \rho_1|^{k_1} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{k_3} \\ f(r) = r \cdot m(r) = r \cdot C_0 \cdot |r - \rho_1|^{k_1} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{k_2} \cdot |r - \rho_2|^{k_3}, \end{cases} \quad (100)$$

where

$$k_i = \frac{\mu_1 \rho_i^2 - \mu_2}{P'(\rho_i)} = \frac{\mu_1 \rho_i^2 - \mu_2}{-3\mu_2 \varphi_i^2 + 2\varphi_1 \rho_i + \mu_2}. \quad (101)$$

Feature	Case A: Male Indifference ($\mu_2 = 0$)	Case B: Male Sensitivity ($\mu_2 \neq 0$)
Stability condition	$\varphi_2 < \mu_1$	$\varphi_1 < \mu_1 - 0.75$
Constraint on females	Severe: if $\varphi_2 > 0.15 \cdot \mu_1$, venue collapses	Relaxed: Higher φ_2 is tolerated because μ_2 compensates
Viability threshold	High (Fragile): Tipping point is close to equilibrium	Low (Relaxed): Tipping point is pushed towards zero
Behaviour under shock	If ratio r drops slightly, males stay while females leave, triggering a “death spiral”	If ratio r drops, some males leave, reducing r and enabling recovery
Interpretation	Describes a casual “meat market” of utter fungibility	Describes a stable community with shared norms and social bonds

This would tend to convalidate the presence of the $\mu_2 \cdot \frac{m}{f}$ after all: males also shy away from ‘unbalanced’ or ‘creepy’ venues, validating the assumptions enshrined in (1).

References

- [1] Becker, G. S. (1957). *The economics of discrimination*. University of Chicago Press.
- [2] Bollobás, B., & Riordan, O. (2006). The critical probability for random Voronoi percolation in the plane is $1/2$. *Probability Theory and Related Fields*, 136(3), 417–468.
- [3] Broadbent, S. R., & Hammersley, J. M. (1957). Percolation processes. *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 53(3), 629–641.
- [4] Buchanan, J. M. (1965). An economic theory of clubs. *Economica*, 32(125), 1–14.
- [5] Junghanns, J. (2026). *Gender Balance at Naturist Venues* [Interactive Wolfram Demonstrator]. Wolfram Cloud. <https://wolframcloud.com/obj/james.junghanns/Published/Gender%20Balance%20At%20Naturist%20Venues.nb>
- [6] Karush, W. (1939). *Minima of functions of several variables with inequalities as side constraints* [Master's thesis, University of Chicago].
- [7] Kuhn, H. W., & Tucker, A. W. (1951). Nonlinear programming. In *Proceedings of the second Berkeley symposium on mathematical statistics and probability* (pp. 481–492). University of California Press.
- [8] Nick and Lins. (n.d.). *Destination Clothes Free* [YouTube channel]. YouTube. Retrieved February 1, 2026, from <https://www.youtube.com/@destinationclothesfree>
- [9] Nick and Lins. (n.d.). *Naked Wanderings* [YouTube channel]. YouTube. Retrieved February 1, 2026, from <https://www.youtube.com/@NakedWanderings>
- [10] Pollen, A. (2021). *Nudism in a cold climate: The visual culture of naturists in mid-20th century Britain*. Atelier Editions.
- [11] Rudin, W. (1976). *Principles of mathematical analysis* (3rd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- [12] Schelling, T. C. (1971). Dynamic models of segregation. *The Journal of Mathematical Sociology*, 1(2), 143–186.
- [13] Sundman, K. F. (1912/13). *Mémoire sur le problème des trois corps*. *Acta Mathematica*, 36, 105–179. DOI:10.1007/BF02422379.
- [14] Verhulst, P.-F. (1838). Notice sur la loi que la population suit dans son accroissement. *Correspondance Mathématique et Physique*, 10, 113–121.
- [15] Voronoi, G. (1908). Nouvelles applications des paramètres continus à la théorie des formes quadratiques. Deuxième mémoire: Recherches sur les paralléloèdres primitifs. *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik*, 134, 198–287.